

Underwater Flash Lidar for Cultural Heritage Site Preservation

Eleonoor Bosch
Centre Suisse d'électronique et
Microtechnique
Neuchâtel, Switzerland
eleonoor.bosch@csem.ch

David Nguyen
Centre Suisse d'électronique et
Microtechnique
Neuchâtel, Switzerland
david.nguyen@csem.ch

Jannis Holzer
Centre Suisse d'électronique et
Microtechnique
Neuchâtel, Switzerland
jannis.holzer@csem.ch

Christophe Meier
Centre Suisse d'électronique et
Microtechnique
Neuchâtel, Switzerland
christophe.meier@csem.ch

Stéphane Humbert
Centre Suisse d'électronique et
Microtechnique
Neuchâtel, Switzerland
stephane.humbert@csem.ch

Christophe Pache
Centre Suisse d'électronique et
Microtechnique
Neuchâtel, Switzerland
christophe.pache@csem.ch

Regular monitoring of archaeological sites is crucial due to threats from human interference, meteorological events, invasive species, and climate change. Underwater sites in shallow waters are challenging to monitor regularly due to risks of collision with submerged rocks or structures. Autonomous vehicles like unmanned surface vehicles (USVs), unmanned aerial vehicle (UAVs), and remotel operated vehicles (ROVs) equipped with 3D imaging sensors offer reliable, safe, and cost-effective solutions for surveying these areas.

This study introduces a USV equipped with a flash lidar for underwater applications. Preliminary measurements were conducted at Les Argilliez, a UNESCO World Cultural Heritage site which is facing erosion and an invasive mussel species.

Regular 3D mapping is being performed to analyze changes in lakebed morphology and wooden pile structure and placement. The lidar system, enclosed in a watertight cylinder, uses direct-time-of-flight to measure depth with a 128x128 pixel array and adjustable field of view (FoV).

Test campaigns demonstrated the lidars effectiveness in capturing detailed 3D point clouds of the lakebed and wooden posts, allowing measurement of width, length, orientation, and surrounding morphology. Regular surveys will continue throughout 2025, providing an effective solution for underwater archaeological research.

Keywords—flash lidar, USV, survey, mapping, cultural heritage, bathymetry

I. INTRODUCTION

During the Neolithic and Bronze ages several settlements existed on marshy land beside rivers and lakes in central Europe. Because these areas were prone to flooding, structures were built on wooden piles to lift them above changing water levels. Remains of these pile dwellings have been found in 111 locations around Europe and are protected as UNESCO historic sites, 56 of these sites are in Switzerland [1]. The pile dwelling sites provide clues about the prehistoric settlements and often contain other artifacts such as pottery and tools used by their inhabitants [2,3]. Two examples of wooden piles from a now-submerged pile dwelling site are shown in Fig. 1.

Efforts to track the state of submerged sites, such as those found in Lac Neuchâtel, Switzerland, for the sake of their preservation involve monitoring the site for signs of erosion, invasive species, and human or weather inflicted damage. Because the sites are generally in shallow water locations, monitoring has frequently been done by manual inspections and photo documentation performed by divers, or photos

taken above the water surface from a boat or drone [4]. 3D imaging techniques such as photogrammetry, sonar, and bathymetric lidar have the potential to provide detailed information about the state of the site, but the technologies carry trade-offs in terms of cost efficiency and point cloud resolution. As has been explored in several case studies, maturation of 3D imaging technologies provides potential for 3D reconstruction of submerged cultural heritage sites, risk assessment, documentation for archiving, archaeological investigations, and the opportunity to share the site map with the public [5,6,7,8].

Automatic deployment of such survey systems could further reduce cost of monitoring sites, and comparison of the 3D reconstructions could be performed by trained algorithms. Applications of machine learning to cultural heritage site monitoring a preservation is an emerging topic and could enable automated identification of changes in site models [9,10].

Photogrammetry has been performed at several pile dwelling sites and provides very high-resolution point cloud data, sub-mm in ideal conditions, but 1-5 mm is typical [3, 11]. However, it is costly in terms of diver's time as well as computing resources, and imaging quality is dependent on water transparency and weather conditions. Even a small area survey of tens of square meters can take hours to fully capture. Photogrammetry is also highly susceptible to sunlight refraction through water, degrading the digital reconstruction [12]. The overall time and resources needed to complete a

Fig. 1. Example of submerged wooden piles at Les Argilliez. In the bottom left a terra-cotta brick placed by divers. Photo credit: F. Langenegger, OARC.

photogrammetric survey over a large area may hinder its use for frequent monitoring and inspection needs.

Sonar technology is also increasingly used for monitoring underwater cultural heritage sites, offering solutions for imaging and mapping in conditions where visibility is limited [13]. High-frequency systems like synthetic aperture sonar achieve resolutions of 1–5 cm but are affected by environmental factors like multipath interference and seabed composition. While efficient for large areas, sonar requires significant post-processing and is costly to deploy [14].

Structured light has also been explored for cultural heritage site mapping and reconstruction and shows promising resolution and precision [15]. This system, at 1.2 m x 0.7 m x 0.5 m is large, mounted to a remotely operated vehicle (ROV), and is limited in measurement range. It has similar limitations as photogrammetry in that clear conditions are required but additionally relies on precise ROV piloting. The system would not be suitable for sites submerged in very shallow water, such as Les Argilliez.

Lidar has shown promise in monitoring submerged cultural heritage sites, offering precise mapping capabilities even in challenging underwater environments [16]. By using laser pulses, lidar can penetrate water to create detailed 3D models of submerged structures, aiding in their documentation and preservation. However, its effectiveness is influenced by water clarity, depth, and the cost of deploying aerial platforms. Using aerial lidar platforms is further limited by altitude restrictions, which reduce the resolution for shallow and detailed features, and weather conditions like strong winds, which can disrupt accurate data collection [16,17].

A flash lidar system was developed and optimized for collecting 3D point cloud data in shallow water from a medium-sized unmanned surface vehicle (USV). The project aimed at developing a system for efficient survey which would enable monitoring and could provide indications of areas with need for further attention. Comparison of lakebed profiles taken along an erosion front near the site empowers local authorities to intervene when further site protection is warranted.

The system is built to be deployed for regular survey of the Les Argilliez site in Lac Neuchâtel which dates to the Classical Cortaillod (3841-3817 BC) and Late Cortaillod (around 3500 BC) cultures. Divers have identified 4,834 wooden piles over a 7000 m² area ranging from 2 m to 3 m depth below the water surface [4], serving as the ideal test bed for the bathymetric lidar.

This paper provides a description of the full USV-mounted system and presents the performance demonstrated by the lidar from the first surveys of the site.

II. LIDAR AND USV SURVEY PLATFORM

The USV platform consists of several sensors and communication systems which enable synchronized data collection facilitating georeferencing of the point cloud images. Fig. 2 shows the block diagram of the systems onboard the USV, including the following:

- USV autonomous control software: QGroundControl (<https://qgroundcontrol.com>)
- Global navigation satellite system (GNSS): Emlid Reach RS2
- Navigation controller: PixHawk Cube Orange

Fig. 2. USV mounted system block diagram

- Inertial navigation system (INS): SBG systems Ekinox Micro
- Single beam echo-sounder: AirMar SS510
- Lidar and camera: CSEM Airswim system, GoPro
- LAN switch and WiFi radio

A. Vehicle and navigation system

The BathyDrone Sumo (Fig. 3) was selected to carry several payloads including the lidar (Fig. 3, top right), batteries, the INS and antennae, a reference sonar, and an onboard PC. Its dimensions are 128 cm x 80 cm x 60 cm, and the weight is 28 kg (without the lidar). It can either be remotely controlled or programmed to follow pre-defined trajectories using open-source software, QGroundControl which transmits instructions to the PixHawk Cube Orange navigation controller. The USV uses its inertial measurement unit (IMU) coupled with a real-time kinematic (RTK) GNSS for autonomous navigation. It has a maximum speed of 1 m/s.

B. Communication network and synchronization

An INS which has network time protocol (NTP) enabled was used such that all devices on the shared network had continuously synchronized onboard time, including the lidar which also used NTP over ethernet communications. The RTK INS has dual antennae heading accuracy of 0.4° horizontal position accuracy of 1 cm, thus image stitching could be performed using the timestamped point cloud and INS data.

Fig. 3. BathyDrone Sumo operating in Lac Neuchâtel and the lidar mounted in its waterproof case (top right)

C. Flash lidar

The flash lidar is a direct time-of-flight system with a CMOS-based single photon avalanche diode (SPAD) array developed at the Fondazione Brun Kessler [18]. The 128 x 128-pixel focal plane array is comprised of four 64 x 64 pixel SPADs which interface to a system on chip. The system can capture images at a rate of 10Hz and has an adjustable field of view between 10° and 40° which enables optimization of the optical parameters for the depth and clarity of the water, as well as the desired spatial resolution.

The lidar integrates a pulsed laser at 532 nm, which emits nanosecond pulses. The software and backend processing schemes allow time-gating and multiple-echo detection to enable imaging in turbid conditions. For each image, a histogram of photon counts is built with respect to the distance for each pixel. A point cloud is then computed by identifying the peak position in the histogram. An intensity image can also be obtained from the same data by computing the peak energy.

The USV carries an 10,000 Ah lithium polymer battery which easily supplies the 50 W needed to run the lidar during continuous imaging.

When inside the waterproof casing, the lidar measures 23 cm in diameter and 25 cm tall, weighs 18 kg and is approximately neutrally buoyant. A GoPro is mounted directly to the lidar case to enable simultaneous photo capture of the lakebed. When the lidar case is mounted to the BathyDrone Sumo with an aluminium post, the exit window is about 30 cm below the water surface, enabling imaging from 1 m water depth.

Lidar images are stitched together by transforming the pointcloud data based on the INS information. Then they are loaded into Cloud Compare software for visualization.

III. SURVEY AND RESULTS

Regular surveys of the Les Argilliez site at Lac Nauchâtel are planned for monitoring the erosion front present near the site. The surveys are intended to demonstrate the lidar performance and provide information for the local authorities to act against erosion for the preservation of the cultural heritage site when and where necessary. Four depth profiles were marked as being of particular interest and are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Survey mission lines for tracking erosion at Les Argilliez in Lac Neuchâtel

Thus, the survey missions have been planned to capture these four parts of the erosion front to compare depth profiles at regular intervals throughout 2025.

The profile labelled B in Fig. 4 also has a line of 25 terra cotta bricks which were placed with roughly even spacing on the lakebed by divers. These serve as clearly identifiable underwater markers, as well as known-dimension objects for monitoring movement in the lakebed and for evaluating the lidar performance in terms of measurement accuracy.

A. Preliminary measurements

Initial measurements at Les Argilliez comprised a feasibility study of the lidar and USV system to confirm the lidar performance in real conditions and validate point cloud stitching using the GNSS data.

Fig. 5. Preliminary test campaign point cloud data (orange) and GoPro images (green) Two terra cotta bricks from line B (Figure 4) can be seen in both datasets. Photo credit: F. Langenegger, OARC.

A single survey of the four identified erosion lines which is performed autonomously by the USV takes less than 15 minutes. Figure 5 shows a portion of the stitched images taken during initial campaigns. Both lidar point cloud data (orange gradient) and GoPro image data (green-blue photos) are shown. Two of the terra cotta bricks from line B (Figure 4) are identifiable in both images. The lidar shows a depth measurement of about 1.5 m at the tallest points on the bricks, and about 1.67 m at the lakebed next to them, with a few centimetres of variation due to rocks and quagga mussel populations surrounding the bricks.

The morphology of a large rock is visible in the top right of the point cloud data, but the Gro Pro image has much lower contrast making the rock less visible among other features in the photo.

B. Subsequent campaigns

Another survey mission at the lake demonstrated the system capability for mapping the individual wooden piles found at site. In Figure 6, a GoPro image is shown which was taken at the same time as a lidar image of two piles. The piles

Fig. 6. Identification of wooden piles in depthmap and point cloud lidar data. a) GoPro image of two piles from above b) Depthmap data from lidar c) point cloud data from lidar showing height of piles.

are difficult to identify in the GoPro image but are distinguishable in the lidar depth map and in the 3D point cloud. From the point cloud in particular, the piles relative position and orientation, as well as their prominence above the lakebed can be seen and measured.

C. Survey challenges

Despite moderate size and weight, the USV system is susceptible to wavy and windy conditions on the lake, which impact its ability to follow straight mission lines. Calm weather days must be selected for survey to enable execution of the mission, avoid risk of waves and water splashing over the boat, and to avoid high speed angular motion which would induce significant motion blur in the lidar measurements.

In addition, because communication with onboard electronics is over WiFi, the system range is about 45 m from the operator before the data latency is too long for manipulation of the system. Images can be collected onboard without this connection, but commands and images can only be transmitted over the wireless network when the system is close enough.

IV. CONCLUSION

The flash lidar system employed for survey of the Les Argilliez cultural heritage site enables efficient monitoring of the submerged wooden piles and lakebed below. Surveys can be conducted in less than 15 minutes, and with a pixel footprint of less than 0.6 cm square at 2 m water depth, the lidar data provides sufficient resolution to identify changes in subsea structures or the lakebed profile.

The USV-mounted lidar will continue to be used at the site for comparison of erosion line profile measurements throughout 2025.

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